

IXI software

<http://www.ixi-software.net>

Abstract

We are interested in exhibiting our programs at your demo section at the conference. We believe that the subject of your conference is precisely what we are experimenting with in our musical software.

Keywords

Further info on our website:

<http://www.ixi-software.net>.

INTRODUCTION

IXI software is a network of experimentalists in the field of computer music and computer music software. We produce various types of work in our studios but we are mainly concerned with producing small prototypes or applications where we concentrate on new modes of interactivity in music software. These applications can be found on this site and downloaded in both PC and Mac format. However, our field of interest varies from producing interactive and generative music to creating software for music production and specialised VST plugins. Everything is possible as we are in strong partnership with the users of ixi-software and always open to new suggestions and ideas that push the development.

To support the innovation we have started ixi-label. The label will only feature music produced with ixi software, whether it was used to create just a sample or a whole track. Releases will be a mix of both MP3 and vinyl/CD albums. Our first release will be available in the spring of 2002 and will feature music from those who have beta tested the software. As we've discovered, musicians are using the software in a variety of ways - so expect a vast range of music distractions over the next year!

WHAT IXI IS ON ABOUT...

New modes of interactivity are our main fields of interest and as such can be divided into two distinct but related categories:

a) interactivity in the sense of innovative visual interfaces triggering musical structures

b) physical interfaces such as touch screens, datagloves, control pads, various types of control sensors, plus biofeedback sensors such as heart rate monitors, eye trackers and other sensors measuring the bodily state.

We started working on our concept after a long period of personal discontent with how homogeneously traditional computer music software is built, namely using the typical metaphors from the physical world, often in a strangely uncritical way. Thus we are faced with various types of sequencers using the metaphor of the score, or a multitude of instruments or plug-ins that are like a virtual copies of the physical instruments or hardware modules.

Of course, such applications often provide great functions and solutions that are ingenious in themselves, but our aim is to create some instruments of and for the computer itself, something that does not necessarily have any real-world predecessor. The computer opens up an incredibly wide space in which all thinkable instruments and sound-worlds can be created.

There are hardly any imaginable limits for what can be designed for the computer, but a lot of temporary technological ones. ixi are exploring and working with various types of technology, like VST development, Midi controllers (virtual and physical), making stand-alone applications, networked communication, Max/Msp, Supercollider, but currently we are mainly concerned with making small instruments (or prototypes) with non-conventional interfaces that can be used as catalysis engines for innovative and creative musical output.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ixi Software, online at <<http://www.ixi-software.net>>